

Investment Strategies In Stock Market

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 7

Special Issue : 1

Month : February

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Jemima Suganthi, M.
“Investment Strategies
in Stock Market.”
*Shanlax International
Journal of Commerce*,
vol. 7, no. S1, 2019,
pp. 145–149.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.2552244](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2552244)

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Abstract

Investment is a future return. Investment in stock market is considered to be riskier factor than any other investment. Stock market changes day to day. The person who are investing in stock market need to careful and have to bear any risk if occurs because the price of the share changes simultaneously. That is why investment in stock market is referred to a risk market. This paper summarises on investment, risk factor, various opportunities in investment.

Introduction

Over the past few years, Investing is a method of purchasing assets to gain profit in the form of reasonably predictable income (dividends interest, or rentals) and appreciation over the long term. There is no single strategy followed by investors in the stock market. Everyone has a different risk-return profile and hence uses the best suitable plan for investment. Some investors believe in calculations while others believe on graphical predictions.

Objectives

- To determine the perception of investor for stock market.
- To know about the risk of investors.
- To understand the investment strategy of common investors in the stock market.

History of the Stock Market

A stock market is “a place where stocks, bonds, or other securities are bought and sold. A share of stock informally referred to as “stock,” is a share in the ownership of a corporation. Stocks entitle the owner to voting rights in major company decisions. Stocks can be bought and sold at a price determined by the financial success of the corporation and the overall demand for the corporation’s stock. The New York Stock Exchange (NYSE) was the first stock market to be established in the United States, tracing its roots back to 1792.

Pros of Investment in the Stock Market

Earn More Money

Many investors have heard tales of people getting in on the ground floor with massive companies like Apple and Google and then making incredible amounts of money. If you play your cards right, you too can create wealth through the stock market.

Unmatched Liquidity

Unlike other investments, such as real estate and CDs, investors can easily access money in the stock market. Within seconds, you can sell, buy and trade as you see fit. Its nothing but you easily sell the stock and can make money.

Flexibility

Investing in the stock market can help bolster your entire financial portfolio. You can allocate your funds to your retirement. Best of all, these funds then remain tax-free until you use them. There are many different ways to allocate your funds, which can help you become more financially secure.

Cons of Investment in the Stock Market

The Market Can Be Volatile

In the stock market, there are winners and losers. Winners can make much money, but those who lose can see all of their investment disappear. If you want to invest in the stock market, you should be ready to bear risk with financial stability.

Stock Market Crashes

Investors can expect daily volatility in the stock market. However, when they do happen, it can take years to recover. Potential investors need only to look back to 2008 to see how badly the market can crash in a matter of hours. While the market has retained since then, it took years for investors to rebuild their portfolios.

Financial Investment Opportunities

Shares of Stock

Stockbrokers will buy or sell stock on behalf of an individual for a commission, and also they provide assistance to their customers. Investment in stocks can be a risk. This possibility of high returns and the unpredictability of the market are enticing to excitable investors however, with wise decision-making, the stock market can be a stable, long-term investment opportunity as well.

Bonds

Bonds are a loan, granted by the investor (“the holder”), to a corporation or individual (“the issuer,” usually the government). The loan agreement includes a specified amount of time, after which the bond is said to “mature”. Because of bonds’ stability, guaranteed ROI, and because they are unaffected by the stock market. It is popular as long-term investments, and during uncertain financial times.

Certificates of Deposit

Certificates of deposit (informally referred to as “CDs” or “CODs”) are investments made in banks or credit unions in the form of a long-term savings account. A COD works very much the investor loans a bank a principle amount, on which the bank pays interest.

Mutual Funds

Mutual Funds are an investment in a fund, managed by a fund manager that is invested in many different small investments. The fund manager trades these small investments regularly, generating a return for the fund principle. The investors will be paid a portion of this return. The value of a mutual fund is determined by its net asset value (NAV), or the combined worth of the fund's holdings (the fund's investment portfolio). Mutual Funds are usually a medium-risk, medium-return investment.

The 5 Strategies of Investment

1. General Trading: Anticipating or participating in the moves of the market as a whole, as reflected in the familiar "averages."
2. Selective Trading: Picking out stocks which, throughout a period of a year or less, will do better than the market.
3. Long-Pull Selection: Picking out companies which will prosper over the years far more than the average enterprise. (These are often referred to as "growth stocks.").
4. Bargain Purchases: Selecting issues which are selling considerably below their true value, as measured by reasonably dependable techniques.

Top Companies in Stock Market

Company Name	Last Price	% Chg	52wk High	52wk Low	MarketCap (Rs. cr)
TCS	1,897.05	1.23	2,273.00	1,320.20	711,846.14
Reliance	1,103.00	0.36	1,328.75	872.10	699,143.37
HDFC Bank	2,117.55	-0.01	2,219.05	1,830.00	575,868.02
HUL	1,785.00	0.27	1,870.50	1,281.60	386,389.84
ITC	281.70	0.34	322.70	251.30	344,995.63
HDFC	1,972.00	0.04	2,051.00	1,646.00	339,079.73
Infosys	671.35	1.60	754.95	503.13	293,288.24
SBI	296.00	-0.50	334.80	232.00	264,167.79
Kotak Mahindra	1,242.40	-0.34	1,424.00	992.50	236,993.28
ICICI Bank	367.85	0.63	375.25	256.50	236,904.63
Maruti Suzuki	7,359.00	1.68	9,922.85	6,501.65	222,300.72
Larsen	1,384.00	-0.38	1,469.60	1,183.40	194,067.29
ONGC	147.65	1.37	212.90	134.75	189,482.72
Axis Bank	637.30	2.82	676.90	477.50	163,780.35
Bajaj Finance	2,553.25	-1.01	2,995.10	1,514.40	147,569.78
Wipro	323.45	-0.05	344.00		

India SENSEX Stock Market Index

SENSEX increased 159 points or 0.44% to 36009 on Tuesday, January 8 from 35850 in the previous trading session. Historically, the India SENSEX Stock Market Index reached an all-time high of 38896.63 in August of 2018 and a record low of 113.28 in December of 1979.

	Components	Price		Day	Year	Capital	Date
TTMT	Tata Motors	175.35	4.40	2.57%	-59.92%	10.1B	Jan/08
TCS	TCS	1,897.90	21.05	1.12%	-29.94%	112B	Jan/07
RIL	Reliance Industries	1,103.45	4.40	0.40%	17.28%	109B	Jan/07
HDFCB	Hdfc Bank	2,120.65	3.20	0.15%	13.79%	73.5B	Jan/07
ITC	ITC	281.65	0.70	0.25%	4.10%	49.3B	Jan/07
HUVR	Hindustan Unilever	1,784.95	3.25	0.18%	31.12%	49.1B	Jan/07
INFO	Infosys	671.70	10.65	1.61%	-35.50%	42.9B	Jan/07
SBIN	State Bank of India	296.30	-1.35	-0.45%	-2.63%	33.6B	Jan/07
MSIL	Maruti Suzuki	7,362.05	127.55	1.76%	-21.54%	32.5B	Jan/07
ONGC	Oil & Natural Gas Corporation	147.85	2.15	1.48%	-24.95%	31.8B	Jan/07
ICICIBC	Icici Bank	367.70	2.50	0.68%	17.63%	27.7B	Jan/07
LT	Larsen & Toubro	1,383.80	-4.25	-0.31%	3.83%	25.7B	Jan/07
COAL	Coal India	234.50	-2.00	-0.85%	-22.87%	23.2B	Jan/07
AXSB	Axis Bank	637.45	17.85	2.88%	12.76%	21.8B	Jan/07
SUNP	Sun Pharmaceuticals	430.80	-3.00	-0.69%	-26.55%	21.1B	Jan/07
WPRO	Wipro	324.25	-0.20	-0.06%	2.22%	19.8B	Jan/07
BHARTI	Bharti Airtel	324.95	2.50	0.78%	-36.26%	19.8B	Jan/07
NTPC	NTPC	148.60	2.85	1.96%	-15.90%	19B	Jan/07
MM	Mahindra & Mahindra	729.55	3.95	0.54%	-4.32%	14.5B	Jan/07
GAIL	GAIL	357.10	3.95	1.12%	-28.72%	11.6B	Jan/07
BJAUT	Bajaj Auto	2,658.55	-75.65	-2.77%	-18.03%	11B	Jan/07
TATA	Tata Steel	485.50	-2.15	-0.44%	-37.14%	10.3B	Jan/07
HMCL	Hero Moto	2,957.95	-29.90	-1.00%	-21.11%	8.51B	Jan/07
CIPLA	Cipla	514.05	1.25	0.24%	-16.50%	7.45B	Jan/07
DRRD	Dr.Reddys Laboratories	2,558.65	-41.35	-1.59%	4.10%	5.94B	Jan/07

Conclusion

The stock market can be very lucrative. By following a clear set of rules, an investor can produce a consistent gain through day trading. A basic understanding of the psyche of investors, along with diligent research can make swing trading an effective investing strategy.

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